

ASSESSMENT OF POSTOPERATIVE EFFECT OF CORNEAL CROSS-LINKING ON KERATOCONUS USING THE ABCD GRADING SYSTEM

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17731093>

Keywords

Corneal cross-linking, Keratoconus

Article History

Received on 26 May 2025

Accepted on 26 June 2025

Published on 03 July 2025

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Abstract

Objective: To monitor changes in parameters of ABCD (A:Anterior radius of curvature of cornea, B:Posterior radius of curvature of cornea, C:Corneal thickness, D:Distant visual acuity) grading system during one-year follow up after corneal cross-linking.

Study Design: Prospective Cohort Study

Place and Duration of Study: Armed Forces Institute of Ophthalmology, Rawalpindi Pakistan. One year duration from January 2023- January 2024.

Methodology: A total of 270 patients having keratoconus were enrolled after taking informed consent. Patients underwent cross-linking and were examined at baseline visit and followed up at 3,6 and 12 months after CXL (Corneal Collagen Cross-linking). All patients had standard CXL protocol with visual acuity in log Mars and Scheimpflug tomography carried out at each visit. ABCD grading was monitored throughout.

Results: In 270 patients with mean age of 23.8 ± 4.37 years, Parameter A (Anterior radius of curvature of cornea) increased in first three months from 6.28 (median) to 6.31 however by 12 months it dropped slightly to 6.30. Parameter B (Posterior radius of curvature of cornea) and C (Corneal thickness) showed progression (median increased from 4.6 to 4.8 and 417 to 430 respectively in 03 months) while parameter D (Distant visual acuity) initially declined (0.2 median to 0.1) but became stable later to pre-CXL value of 0.2.

INTRODUCTION

The word keratoconus is derived from the Greek word meaning 'cone-shaped' cornea¹. Keratoconus is a non-inflammatory disorder in which some part of cornea becomes thinner and bulges forward in a cone-shaped manner resulting in image distortion².

Several environmental and familial factors are associated with an increased risk of developing keratoconus which includes allergy, atopy and chronic

eye rubbing¹. Keratoconus prevalence is as high as 26.8% among Vernal keratoconjunctivitis patients³. As the disease progresses, pigmented iron deposits known as Fleischer's ring can be seen on ophthalmic examination. Sometimes fine vertical stress lines, known as Vogt's striae can appear in moderate keratoconus. Advanced stages are characterized by Munson's sign, an abnormal light reflection known as Rizzuti's sign, corneal scarring and corneal hydrops⁴.

Current diagnostic imaging modalities include corneal topography and tomography, which are often used in conjunction with corneal biomechanical measurements and epithelial thickness mapping which become abnormal in corneal ectasia⁵.

Corneal collagen crosslinking (CXL) is a minimally invasive treatment that can be employed to stabilize corneal ectatic disorders or post refractive surgery ectasia⁶. The purpose of UVA-riboflavin induced CXL is to increase the biomechanical stiffness of the cornea⁷. It allows to generate extra bonds and new chemical chains in the anterior corneal stroma, which then improves its strength and stability⁸.

One method to classify KC was the Amsler classification (1950). The latest classification was introduced by Belin and Duncan in 2016, who proposed a new KC grading system based on the analyses of four parameters; anterior (A) and posterior (B) curvature of cornea, thinnest corneal pachymetry (C) and the distance best-corrected visual acuity (D)⁹. The aim of the study was to monitor changes in parameters of ABCD grading system during one-year follow up after corneal cross-linking.

METHODOLOGY

The prospective study was conducted at Armed Forces Institute of Ophthalmology (AFIO) Rawalpindi, from January 2023 to January 2024 after approval from the Ethical Committee (ERC/IERB approval certificate number 298 dated 09 December, 2022). Sample size was calculated using “*OpenEpi calculator online for cohort studies*” taking the confidence level 95%, margin of error 5%, power 80%, mean 1.4 with standard deviation 0.77 of the parameter using reference article.¹⁰ The estimated sample size came out to be 270.

Inclusion Criteria: The study included patients with keratoconus of either gender, aged from 18 to 35 years who haven't undergone any ocular procedure before.

Exclusion criteria: Patients under 18 years of age, having corneal pachymetry less than 350 microns, corneal scarring, history of ocular trauma or surgery were excluded from the study.

Keratoconus patients visiting OPD being planned for cross linking were randomly selected using simple random sampling technique. Patients meeting inclusion criteria and planned for corneal cross-linking were enrolled for subjective study. After

detailed information, written informed consent was taken from all the participants.

After a detailed clinical examination, corneal CXL was performed. Under sterile conditions, the patient's eye was anesthetized and the corneal epithelium was removed manually. We employed the standard Dresden protocol in which (0,1% Riboflavin, 1,1% HPMC) was instilled every 2 min for 30 min, after which a 9-mm diameter beam of ultraviolet A (UV-A) radiance of 3 mW/cm² was irradiated for 30 min in six 5-min intervals with a simultaneous drip of riboflavin. After the procedure, the cornea was rinsed with a balanced salt solution and a silicone hydrogel bandage contact lens was applied. Postoperatively, topical corticosteroids were used for 1-4 months, depending on the corneal haze. One preoperative and three postoperative examinations were performed in each patient. Postoperatively, the patients were scanned 3 months, 6 months and a year after the procedure. At each visit, the participants underwent a slit-lamp examination, corneal tomography (Pentacam) and visual acuity testing. On Pentacam, the Belin ABCD progression display was observed, which enabled the analysis of parameters A, B, C, and D, after manual input of the best-corrected visual acuity into the system for each visit.

RESULTS

In the study, a total of 270 patients undergoing a CXL procedure were enrolled to monitor the changes in four key parameters (A, B, C and D). The average age of participants was 23.8 ± 4.37 years, and measurements on these variables were taken at four different times: before the surgery (pre-CXL) and then at 3, 6 and 12 months following the operation.

For parameter A, its median rose from 6.28 pre-CXL to 6.31 three months later and stood at 6.33 after six months; however, by 12 months it dropped slightly to 6.30. This means it increased after an early period (up to 6 months) and then fell slightly downwards but for all time intervals, it remained significantly higher than what was recorded at baseline meaning that CXL had a long-term positive effect on it. On the side of parameter B, before surgery this was recorded as 4.6. After undergoing a CXL procedure, it increased significantly as seen in both instances of 3 months post-CXL (4.8) as well as 6 months after CXL (4.8). However, by the end of year one follow-up visit it went

back down to similar levels (4.5) seen before operation.

This shows that there were some fluctuations but in general a significant change took place although initial improvements on variable B did not last throughout the entire year period. For parameter C, there was a consistent and significant increase in the median values, rising from 417.5 pre-CXL to 430.0 at 3 months, 435.0 at 6 months, and 434.5 at 12 months

post-CXL. This suggests improvement that persisted throughout the 12-month period. Parameter D had a pre-CXL median of 0.2. This value decreased to 0.1 at both 3 and 6 months post-CXL, representing a significant reduction. However, by the 12-month follow-up, the median value returned to 0.2 suggesting that the initial reduction in Variable D was temporary, and the variable eventually returned back to its original state.

Table-I: Comparison of Pre & Post CXL Parameters

	Pre-CXL (Median (IQR))	3-months Post-CXL (Median (IQR))	6-months Post CXL (Median (IQR))	12-months Post-CXL (Median (IQR))	p value
A	6.28 (6.18 - 6.40)	6.31 (6.18 - 6.42) **	6.33 (6.19 - 6.43) **	6.30 (6.19 - 6.42) **	<0.001*
B	4.6 (4.2 - 4.8)	4.8 (4.5 - 5.0) **	4.8 (4.6 - 5.0) **	4.5 (4.2 - 4.8)	<0.001*
C	417.5 (402.0 - 434.0)	430.0 (420.0 - 445.0) **	435.0 (425.0 - 450.0) **	434.5 (425.0 - 451.0) **	<0.001*
D	0.2 (0.1 - 0.2)	0.1 (0.0 - 0.1) **	0.1 (0.0 - 0.1) **	0.2 (0.1 - 0.2)	<0.001*

*p<0.05, significant on Friedman test, **significant Bonferroni adjusted post hoc test results comparing individual time points against preoperative values

DISCUSSION

There is no clear definition of corneal ectasia progression, according to the Global Consensus on Keratoconus and Ectatic Diseases. So far, there are several methods to evaluate the progression of corneal ectasia or to see the efficacy of CXL on ectasias. Early systems used serial topographic analysis alone, whereas many newer systems have used complex keratometric indices to describe the progression.

This study showed that Parameter A initially increased post-CXL, then became static and dropped at a year post-CXL visit but overall remained higher than pre-CXL. Parameter B increased in two successive post-CXL visits but became similar to pre-CXL later. Parameter C improved significantly post-CXL in all visits. Parameter D declined in initial visits after treatment but eventually restored at the last visit.

A study was done to monitor the changes in the ABCD grading system during a one-year follow-up after a corneal cross-linking (CXL) procedure. It showed that there were no significant changes in A, anterior radius curvature in the ABCD grading system. Parameters B, posterior radius curvature and D, best distant corrected visual acuity showed progression postoperatively. Parameter C, pachymetry showed a statistically significant increase at all three

post-CXL visits, but a constant gradual decrease in the value over time¹⁰.

Another study aimed to analyze the postoperative corneal cross-linking results of corneal parameters and the ABCD grading system, depending on the cone location. It showed that parameter A remained relatively stable throughout the follow-up period in both groups. Parameter B and parameter C were significantly increased in both groups postoperatively. Parameter D showed stability at the 6-months post-CXL in the peripheral KC group, while the central and paracentral KC group showed improvement at the 12-month post-CXL visit¹¹.

One article worked on the different CXL protocols for progressive keratoconus and analyzed the post-operative effects using ABCD classification¹².

In another study ABCD grading system was used to evaluate the possible keratoconus progression one year after performed a crosslinking (CXL) and showed no progression in all gradients when compared to the preoperative stage¹³.

One article highlighted the importance of this grading system stating that in contrast to the Amsler-Krumeich classification, this allows an individual grading of each component including the posterior corneal curvature, where early ectatic changes can often be picked up before anterior changes. The

ABCD grading system is useful in discriminating progressive KC from non-progressive¹⁴. One study explored the potential of an additional biomechanical parameter 'E' as an addition to the tomographic ABCD ectasia/keratoconus (KC) staging and found it to detect abnormalities before tomographic changes¹⁵. A relationship was found between anterior corneal surface grade in ABCD system with Kmax in different groups. However, the posterior corneal surface parameter was not correlated with Kmax¹⁶.

In another study they evaluated the sensitivity and specificity of the ABCD progression display for progression of keratoconus and found that all parameters have high sensitivity and specificity except parameter D¹⁷.

The authenticity of ABCD system was further supported by another study stating that ABCD Progression Display has adequate sensitivity and specificity and high predictive capabilities of keratoconus progression. Hence, it can be effectively employed as an initial screening test in adults with keratoconus¹⁸.

LIMITATION OF STUDY

However, this study has a limitation which is a relatively short follow-up period. Many studies have shown that long term follow-up is required post CXL as it can produce corneal changes many years after the procedure.

CONCLUSION

The ABCD grading system provides a good insight into the keratoconus disease severity, taking into account parameters which includes not only the anterior, but also posterior corneal curvatures, corneal thickness profiles, and combining them with functional changes in visual acuity. It can be beneficial in monitoring the KC progression and efficacy of the CXL procedure.

Conflict of Interest: None

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